

THE PROBLEM OF TRANSLATION OF POLITICAL PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS FROM ENGLISH INTO UZBEK

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Annotation: *The place of the current paper is to show a couple of issues of interpretation political phraseological units from English into Uzbek language thinking about them linguacultural features. The language culture of the individual is formed at relationship of marvels "culture of language" and "culture of talk". In its reason the data on norms of made and oral talk, semantic and expressive chances of system, examination of magnificent workmanship, marketing specialist and some various compositions lays.*

Keywords: *political phraseological units, linguaculturalogy, equivalent, culture of discourse, transformation, component.*

Learning the vocabulary of any language is always an interesting learning process. Learning English vocabulary can be boring or interesting. Just take the words from the dictionary and teach them how a poem alone can be a boring thing, but if you will, learn words in a group with friends, this process will seem very interesting and not very difficult occupation, process. In the context of interactive learning, knowledge takes on different forms. On the one hand, they represent certain information about the world around them. The peculiarity of this information is that the student receives it not in the form of a ready-made system from the teacher, but in the process of their own activity. The teacher must create situations in which the student is active, in which he asks, acts. Research on the issues of correspondence between societies what's more, people groups is getting increasingly escalated. In this way, language, being a significant method of concentrating data about the world, simultaneously goes about as the main sign of a specific group. It is in language that the attitude of individuals, their brain research, customs and mores are most obviously communicated. It is a methods for making public writing, the principle archive of data about a specific group. The public mindset is showed in the impression of the characteristics of life, customs, history and culture, basically phraseological units. One of the highlights of sayings is to give individuals an appraisal of the target marvels of the real world, consequently communicating the perspective. In the phraseological units is communicated the particular outlook, a method of judgment, the element sees;

they show the life and life, soul and temper, habits and customs, convictions and strange notions. Etymological and social examination of phraseological units is married to outside factors: the set of experiences of the country, its way of life, regular daily existence, and so forth the Study of phraseological units in the etymological furthermore, social perspective assists with explaining, and at times to set up extra semantic shades with public and social semantics. In the idiomatics of the language, that is, in the layer that is, by definition, nationally specific, the system of values, public morality, attitude to the world, to people, to other peoples is displayed. Phraseological units most clearly illustrate the way of life, geographical location, history, and traditions of a particular community United by a single culture. Issues of translating phraseological units from English into Uzbek, considering their etymological and social attributes, is viewed as quite possibly the most troublesome sorts of interpretation changes. The object of interpretation isn't a language framework as a deliberation, be that as it may, a particular discourse work in another dialect (the first content), based on which another discourse work in another dialect (the interpretation text) is made. The reason for the interpretation is to familiarize the peruser (or audience) who doesn't have the foggiest idea about the first language as intently as conceivable with this content (or the substance of oral discourse). Problems of phraseology are extremely important both for practice and for translation theory; they often present great practical difficulties and arouse great theoretical interest, since they are related to the difference in semantic and stylistic functions performed in different languages by words of the same real meaning, and to the difference in combinations that such words enter into in different languages. This paper discusses only some of the many problems of translating phraseological units. It is usually accepted to indicate the equivalent of a phraseological unit to a word. However, the theory of complete equivalence is becoming obsolete. This does not mean that phraseological units and words have nothing in common, which is considered by the theory of correlation of certain types of phraseological units and words, which, however, is based on slightly different principles. The most characteristic for phraseological turns of stable combinations of words are in principle equal in meaning to a single word, differing from it, as a rule, by a certain expressive and stylistic coloring. Some idioms are translated with the help of partial (relative) equivalence. According to E.F.Arsentyeva, such idiomatic expressions are characterized by the minor differences in terms of phraseological expression of the identical semantics that can have a componential or morphological character (Arsentyeva, 1989: 100) The classification of phraseological units also contains the necessary theoretical knowledge for the translator, with which we can identify the phraseological units in the text, then analyze it and, based on the analysis, give the

most accurate translation in this context. The most legitimate approach is to consider phraseological units in three aspects: semantic, structural grammatical, and component. Taking into account the marked levels, the following types are distinguished: 1) phraseological equivalents (full and partial) - phraseological units with identical semantics, structural and grammatical organization and with identical component composition; Red book - Qizil kitob; The black prince - Qora shahzoda; Black list - Qora ro'yxat; Black diamonds - Qora oltin; Keep quiet - Sir saqlamoq; Make conversation - Manosiz suhbatlashmoq; Milk cow - Sog'in sigir; First think, then speak - Avval o'yla, keyin so'yla; The dog bark, but caravan goes on - It hurar, karvon o'tar; Step by step - Qadam ba qadam. 2) phraseological analogs (full and partial) - phraseological units that express the same or similar meaning, but are characterized by a complete difference in the approximate similarity of the internal form; A black hen lays a white egg - Qora sigir oq sut berar. Cut the melon - foydanib olmoq. Put smb/smith to the test - tekshirib ko'rmoq; Red meat - Qo'y go'shti; Take a fancy to smb - Maftun bo'lmoq; Talk turkey - Ochiqdan-ochiq gapirmoq. 3) non-equivalent phraseological units - phraseological units that do not have correspondences in the phraseological system of another language. To throw up one's cap - do'ppisini osmonga otmoq . Come Yorkshire over smb - Aldamoq, nonni tuya qilmoq Between hawk and buzzard - Oila a'zolarini va xizmatkorlar o'rtasidagi o'rinni egallagan inson; Green room - Teatrda artistlarning kiyinadigan, yasanadigan xonasi; Harley Street - Shifokorlar, tibbiyot dunyosi (Lo'ndondagi ko'pgina mashxur doktorlar yashaydigan ko'cha); Gretna Green marriage - Uydan qochgan sevishganlar o'rtasidagi turmush; Since phraseology stands out for its functions in language and The methods of research are: the overall selection (used in gathering the research material), componential analysis (used in considering the semantic nature of researched units). The primary research methodology includes the methods of descriptive analysis, which consists in collecting and systematizing the collected facts, in their logical comprehension and identification of specific patterns. Comparative method linguistic and extralinguistic characteristics, human emotions and pshraseological-semantic fields. Actuality: The importance of our research is phraseologisms expressing the emotional state of a person. It analyses general semantic feature of a group of phraseological units, various emotional states, linguistic and extralinguistic characteristics, human emotions and pshraseologicalsemantic fields. It is noticeable that a special place in semantic studies of recent times is occupied by the problems of emotional semantics, closely related to the so-called emotional aspect of the human factor in the language. Human emotions are reflected in language.

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